

doi <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6794091>

Vol. 05 Issue 05 May - 2022

Manuscript ID: #0602

PRINCIPALS' AUTHENTIC LEADERSHIP PRACTICES AS CORRELATES OF TEACHERS' ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

*¹Oshia, Eucharia Chinwe,²Chukwudi, Roseline Ujunwa (Ph.D) & ³Obionu, Uchenna Anulika

¹Department of Educational Management and Policy, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria

^{2&3}Department of Educational Foundations, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam, Anambra State, Nigeria

Corresponding author: *Oshia, Eucharia Chinwe
Email: oshiaeucharia@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study investigated principals' authentic leadership practices as correlates of teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses tested at a 0.05 level of significance. A correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 5,286 teachers in 262 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample size of 1,057 teachers which represents 20% of the population was drawn using proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Two sets of instruments titled "Principals' Authentic Leadership Practices Questionnaire (PALPQ) and "Teachers' Organizational Citizenship Behaviour Scale (TOCBS)" was used for data collection. The face validation of the instruments was determined by three experts, two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy and one specialist in Measurement and Evaluation from the Department of Educational Foundations, all in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University. The internal consistencies of the instruments were determined using Cronbach alpha which yielded overall coefficients of 0.84 and 0.82 for (PALPQ) and (TOCBS) respectively. Data analysis was done using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation to answer the research questions and a t-test of correlation to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed among others that there is a strong positive correlation between principals' internalized moral practice and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. It was also found that there is a significant correlation between principals' relational transparency practice and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that the Ministry of Education should develop policies to guide principals in their internalized moral practice to augment the organizational citizenship behaviour of teachers

KEYWORDS

Principals, Authentic Leadership, Practices, Teachers, Citizenship Behaviour

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License.

Introduction

Leadership plays a crucial role in the success of every organization including the education sector. The leadership of the school determines the progress and success of the education sector. Leadership is the act of inspiring, guiding and influencing others to effectively work together for the attainment of the set objectives (Umeozor&Nnebedum, 2022). Leadership entails guiding, directing, motivating and influencing the efforts of others to attain common goals. The leadership of the school formulates rules, develops programmes, and initiates projects and maps out strategies to implement them within a stipulated time. The continuous demand for positive and genuine ways of influencing the behaviour of members of staff to attain common goals in schools places utmost importance on the adoption of authentic leadership.

Authentic leadership is the behaviour that promotes ethical conduct and transparency in communication, decision-making and interactions with followers. Authentic leadership is the act of being sincere, confident and aware of one's limitations in influencing the activities of others to attain set goals. According to Maundu, Namusonge and Simiyu (2018), authentic leadership is the pattern of behaviour that is inspiring, motivating, service-oriented and visionary. Authentic leadership is characterized by collaborative management, high moral behaviour and conscientiousness. An authentic leader has a distinctive ability to understand problems from various perspectives and is capable of directing followers correctly with fairness, honesty and veracity (Northouse cited in Ramalu&Janadari, 2022). The principals exhibit the acts of authentic leadership by empowering teachers to make decisions, motivating and willing to cooperate with them to attain set objectives. Authentic leaders exhibit consistent behaviour of self-discipline, flexible approach and high integrity in dealing with others.

There are components of authentic leadership practices. Several scholars identified authentic leadership practices to include self-awareness, balanced processing, and internalized moral perspective and relational transparency (Shifare, Fyery&Githaiga, 2021; Roncesvalles &Gaerlan, 2020). Internalized moral and relational transparency practices were adopted for the study. Relational transparency is a leadership act of building and maintaining trust and honesty in an interpersonal relationship with others. Kasa, Shamsuddin, Yaakob, Yusof and Sofian (2020) noted that relational transparency means maintaining the authenticity of interpersonal interactions, recognizing errors and maintaining open, transparent communication with others. Relational transparency is the fairness in the dissemination of information to members of staff. According to Maundu, Namusonge and Simiyu (2018), relational transparency is the leadership behaviour of openly sharing information and expressions of one's true thoughts and feelings, while at the same time trying to control the display of inappropriate emotions. The principals who exhibit relational transparency promote open communication and exchange of ideas in the school.

Internalized moral practice is a leadership behavioural pattern that is associated with upholding ethical standards in influencing the efforts of others to attain set goals. According to Kasa et al. (2020), internalized moral perspective referred to a leader who retains coherence between expressed core principles and judgments and demonstrates justice and a strong level of professional practice. The internalized moral practice is characterized by persistence and resilience in promoting good conduct among members of staff. Başaran and Kırıl (2020) pointed out that internalized morality is the act of behaving in harmony with high moral standards in an organization. Roncesvalles and Gaerlan (2020) pointed out that internalized moral practice involves ethical standards and moral behaviors that are congruent with the authentic leader's ethics or standard of behaviour. The moral acts of principals could make teachers reciprocate by exhibiting organizational citizenship behaviour.

Organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) is the execution of tasks beyond the expectations in the workplace. Viko and Nnorom (2020) defined OCB as the execution of extra work that goes above the routine duties prescribed by job descriptions. The authors added that it is the act of going the extra mile in the conduct of one's duties. It is a personal choice to execute duties outside the requirement of the teachers' job description. Boateng, Kyeremeh, Amoako and Batola (2018) defined organizational citizenship behaviour as intentional conduct that goes beyond the formal necessities of the occupation and is useful to the association. Furthermore, Boateng et al. (201) asserted that it is an individual practice that is deliberate and is not specifically or expressly characterized by the formal prize framework. It is the act of undertaking activities that is above the scope of

one's formal duties. Omoankhanlen and Issa (2021) described OCB as a pattern of behaviour in an organisation that is discretionary and goes beyond the specifications of the job. Teachers' OCB reflects putting extra effort into performing jobs beyond their formal job description to achieve educational objectives. In the educational setting, teachers who voluntarily go out of their way to help their students, colleagues and others as they engage in the work of teaching and learning exemplify organizational citizenship behaviour (Ihueze&Unachukwu, 2020). It is a voluntary attitude of engaging activities of beyond the teaching job description.

The teachers display OCB by making contributions during staff meetings, attending school functions that are voluntarily devoting substantial time to offer assistants to students with learning difficulties, assisting to help and mentor new colleagues, willing taking time out of their schedule to assist the principal with administrative tasks, preparation of lesson notes to colleagues who need assistance among others. Yusuf, Yunusa, Yusuf and Mustapha (2022) noted that teachers demonstrate citizenship behaviour through punctuality, assisting other teachers, offering to undertake any urgent work, making innovative suggestions to improve the institution and not complaining about trivial matters, responding promptly to correspondence and not wasting time. It also entails monitoring the workplace for opportunities or threats and making an extra effort to adopt innovative approaches to instructional delivery in the classroom.

The hostile, dishonest and unfriendly attitudes of some secondary school principals toward their teachers could demotivate them from performing additional roles that contribute to the attainment of educational objectives in Anambra State. Ihueze and Unachukwu (2020) observed that some secondary school teachers in Anambra State neglect their duties and exhibit an "I don't care attitude" towards engaging in behaviour that enhances educational improvement. The authors added that the cases of teachers disengaging in activities within their schools seem to prove that OCB among secondary school teachers in Anambra State is low. Perhaps, the undesirable behaviour of teachers could be reciprocal of the unfair treatment of the principals in public secondary schools in Anambra State. To buttress this, Thompson and Unachukwu (2022) observed that teachers, who perceive any form of unfairness in the treatment meted to them by the system may sooner than later begin to exhibit varying degrees of negative behaviour. Sequel to this, Thompson and Unachukwu (2022) noted that some secondary school administrators fail to take into consideration the well-being, needs and emotions of the teachers could make them become disconcerted, thereby developing negative attitudes towards their workplace. The series of principals' unhealthy or unethical behaviours such as being biased, refusing teachers to air their views on school affairs, favouritism and untimely dissemination of communication might be among the contributing factors to unwillingness of teachers to act beyond their formal job description and expectations. It is the problem that prompted the researchers to investigate principals' authentic leadership practices as correlates of teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study is to principals' authentic leadership practices as correlates of teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to find out:

1. Principals' internalized moral practice as correlates of teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.
2. Principals' relational transparency practice as correlates of teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Research questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the correlation between principals' internalized moral practice and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria?
2. What is the correlation between principals' relational transparency practice and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant correlation between principals' internalized moral practice and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant correlation between principals' relational transparency practice and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Method

A correlation research design was adopted for the study. The study was conducted in the 262 public secondary schools in the six education zones in Anambra State, Nigeria. From a population of 5,286 teachers in the 262 public secondary schools in Anambra State, 1,057 teachers from 105 schools which represent 20% of the population were sampled for the study using proportionate stratified random sampling technique.

Two sets of instruments titled "Principals' Authentic Leadership Practices Questionnaire (PALPQ) and "Teachers' Organizational Citizenship Behaviour Scale (TOCBS)" were used for data collection. The instruments were developed from review of related literature and consultation with experts in the field of education. PALPQ which contained 18 items was divided into two Clusters A and B. Cluster A which contained 10 items focused on internalized moral practice and Cluster B had 8 items on relational transparency practice. TOCBS contained 19 items which solicited information on teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour. The two sets of instruments were structured on a four-point rating scale of strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD); which were weighted 4,3,2,1 respectively.

The face validation of the instruments was determined by three experts, two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy and one specialist in Measurement and Evaluation from the Department of Educational Foundations, all in the Faculty of Education, NnamdiAzikiwe University. The suggestions of the experts include separating double-barrel items and rephrasing ambiguous ones. The suggestions guide the final draft of the instrument. The internal consistencies of the instruments were determined using Cronbach Alpha which yielded overall coefficients of 0.83 and 0.85 for Clusters A and B of PALPQ with an overall coefficient value of 0.84 and 0.82 obtained for TOCBS.

The researchers together with three research assistants administered copies of the questionnaires to the respondents using a direct approach. The research assistants are secondary school teachers who were briefed on the nature of the study and guided on the modalities for the data collection. Out of 1,057 copies of the instruments distributed, 1,024 copies representing a 97% return rate were duly completed, retrieved and used for data analysis. Data analysis was done using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation to answer the research questions and t-test of correlation to test the hypotheses. The research questions are interpreted using the coefficient (r) and the size of the relationship by Downie and Heath cited in Nworgu (2015) as shown: 0.80 and above for strong, above 0.30-below 0.80 for moderate and 0.30 and below for weak respectively. For decision on the hypotheses, where the p-value is equal to or less than the level of the significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected but where the p-value is greater than the level of the significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Results

Research Question One: What is the correlation between principals' internalized moral practice and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Pearson r on the Principals' Internalized Moral Practice and Teachers' Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

Variables		N	Principals' Internalized Moral Practice	Teachers' Organizational Citizenship Behaviour	Remarks
Principals' Internalized Moral Practice		1,024	1.00	.815	Strong Positive
Teachers' Organizational Citizenship Behaviour		1,024	.815	1.00	

Table 1 showed a Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of .815. This shows that there is a strong positive correlation between principals' internalized moral practice and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Research Question Two: What is the correlation between principals' relational transparency practice and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Pearson r on the Principals' Relational Transparency Practice and Teachers' Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

Variables		N	Principals' Relational Transparency Practice	Teachers' Organizational Citizenship Behaviour	Remarks
Principals' Relational Transparency Practice		1,024	1.00	.832	Strong Positive
Teachers' Organizational Citizenship Behaviour		1,024	.832	1.00	

Table 2 indicated a Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of .832. This shows that there is a strong positive correlation between principals' relational transparency practice and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant correlation between principals' internalized moral practice and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Table 3: The Summary of t-test for No Significant Correlation between Principals' Internalized Moral Practice and Teachers' Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

	N	Principals' Internalized Moral Practice	Teachers' Organizational Citizenship Behaviour	p-value	α	Remark
Principals' Internalized Moral Practice	1,024	1	.815	0.03	0.05	Rejected
Teachers' Organizational Citizenship Behaviour	1,024	.815	1			

The result in Table 3 shows that the p-value of 0.03 is less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is a significant correlation between principals’ internalized moral practice and teachers’ organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant correlation between principals’ relational transparency practice and teachers’ organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Table 4: The Summary of t-test for No Significant Correlation between Principals’ Relational Transparency Practice and Teachers’ Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

	N	Principals’ Relational Transparency Practice	Teachers’ Organizational Citizenship Behaviour	p-value	∞.	Remark
Principals’ Relational Transparency Practice	1,024	1	.832			
Teachers’ Organizational Citizenship Behaviour	1,024	.832	1	0.02	0.05	Rejected

The result in Table 4 shows that the p-value of 0.02 is less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is a significant correlation between principals’ relational transparency practice and teachers’ organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Discussion

The finding of the study showed that there is a strong positive correlation between principals’ internalized moral practice and teachers’ organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. This is in line with the finding of Roncesvalles and Gaerlan (2020) which indicated that there was a strong relationship between internalized moral practice and teachers’ organizational citizenship behaviour. The high moral integrity of principals has a strong association with the teachers’ organizational citizenship behaviour. The behaviour of principals which behaviors conform to ethical standards and right values inspire teachers to engage in activities beyond their normal duties. It was also found out that there is significant correlation between principals’ internalized moral practice and teachers’ organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Roncesvalles and Gaerlan (2020) which revealed that internalized moral practice has significant relationship with teachers’ organizational citizenship behaviour in higher education. Internalized moral practice which promote good behaviour promote fair and open environment that is appealing to teachers and thus promote their engagement in organizational citizenship behaviour. The principals’ practice of promoting good conducts by rewarding teachers for desirable acts can immensely promote to the act of working beyond job description or expectations among teachers.

The result of the study revealed that there is strong positive correlation between principals’ relational transparency practice and teachers’ organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. The finding is supported by the previous study of Khan, Awan and Ali (2021) who reported that there is a strong positive relationship relational transparency practice and organizational citizenship behaviour. Relational transparency practice of principals engenders mutual interactions and friendly work environment encourage teachers to show the utmost dedication in performing voluntary tasks in school. The more secondary school principals adopt relational transparency practices, the more that the teachers develop a sense of obligation to display organizational citizenship behavior towards their respective learning institutions. It was also reported that there is significant correlation between principals’ relational transparency practice and teachers’ organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Medina,

(2021) there was significant relationship between relational transparency practice and organizational citizenship behaviour. The principals' behaviours of providing timely information to teachers and encouraging them to exchange ideas could them happy and thereby induce their willingness to voluntarily work for the success of the school. The teachers are bound to become more productive by using their energy and time efficiently and being helpful to their colleagues in a school characterized by collegiality engender by the relational transparency practice of principals.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that there was a positive and significant correlation between principals' authentic leadership practices and teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Authentic leadership significantly contributes to teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in secondary schools. The more the principals exhibit authentic leadership to the teachers, the higher they reciprocate by engaging in organizational citizenship behaviour in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. The Ministry of Education should develop policies to guide principals in their internalized moral practice to augment the organizational citizenship behaviour of teachers.
2. Anambra State Chapter of All Nigeria Conference of Principals of Secondary Schools should organize conferences on relational transparency practices for its members to enable them to acquire skills and knowledge of building mutual interactions and developing a friendly work environment that induce teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour.

References

- Başaran, R., & Kırıl, E. (2020). The relationship between authentic leadership and work engagement. *International Journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, 7(2), 351-363. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33200/ijcer.767560>.
- Boateng, P.A., Kyeremeh, A.E., Amoako, E.P. & Batola, D. (2018). Antecedents of authentic leadership and organizational citizenship behaviours in selected institutions in Brong Ahafo Region. *Global Journal of Human Resource Management*, 6(2), 34-51.
- Ihueze, S.I., & Unachukwu, G.O. (2020). Teachers' perception of principals' support for staff development and empowerment of teachers as correlates of teachers' organizational citizenship behaviour in secondary schools in Anambra state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 6(9), 505-511.
- Kasa, M.D., Shamsuddin, M.F., Yaakob, M.F.M., Yusof, M.R. & Sofian, F.N.R.M. (2020). Exploring the influence of a principal's internalized moral perspective towards teacher commitment in Malaysian Secondary Schools. *Journal of Education and e-Learning Research*, 7(3), 323-333.
- Khan, M.A., Awan, R.N. & Ali, G. (2021). Effect of authentic leadership of school heads on teachers' withdrawal and organizational citizenship behaviors: Confirming the mediation of psychological empowerment. *Pakistan Journal of Humanities & Social Sciences Research*, 4(1), 60-72.
- Maundu, M., Namusonge, G.S. & Simiyu, A. N. (2018). Effect of authentic leadership style on employee engagement in public secondary schools, Murang'a County, Kenya. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 5(11), 90-98.
- Medina, M.R. (2021). Authentic leadership: a study of the relationship between authentic leadership and organizational citizenship behavior among research administrators at Research Universities. *Research Management Review*, 32(1), 71-91.
- Omoankhanlen, J.A. & Issa, T.E. (2021). Impression management and organizational citizenship behaviour of Hotels in Rivers State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 6(6), 278-285.
- Ramalu, S.S., & Janadari, N. (2022). Authentic leadership and organizational citizenship behaviour: The role of psychological capital. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 71(2), 365-385.
- Roncesvalles, C.T. & Gaerlan, A.A. (2020). Authentic leadership and teacher morale: impact on organizational citizenship behavior in higher education. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 8(1), 304-314.
- Shifare, H., Fyery, A. & Githaiga, N. (2021). The impact of authentic leadership on employees' organizational citizenship behavior in Ethiopia public service. *International Journal of Research In Business and Social Science*, 10(6), 121-131.
- Thompson, C.C. & Unachukwu, G.O. (2022). Organizational justice as a correlate of teachers' engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 5(1), 23-33.
- Viko, H.J., & Nnorom, G.K. (2020). Job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behaviour of employees in selected Deposit Money Banks of Lagos State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Management, Social Sciences, Peace and Conflict Studies*, 3(3), 349-359.
- Umeozor, U.J., & Nnebedum, C. (2022). Principals' servant and distributed leadership practices as correlates of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Enugu State, Nigeria. *International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods*, 10(3), 584-590.
- Yusuf, L.I., Yunusa, A.F., Yusuf, S. & Mustapha, A.I. (2022). Teachers' citizenship behaviour as determinant of students' academic performance in North-Central, Nigeria. *Mediterranean Journal of Education*, 2(1), 94-104.